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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EVERSE Work Package 5, Task 5.2 (WP5 T5.2), focuses on the development of a comprehensive framework to recognise the contributions of Trainers and Research Software Engineers (RSEs) within the context of Open Science. The primary goal of this framework is to acknowledge and reward scientific work related to research software by leveraging and adapting existing platforms.

This milestone, “*A mechanism for recognition of activities to be easily used in CVs*”, presents a demonstrator of a mechanism enabling third-party recognition in Curriculum Vitae (CVs). It represents a key first step in the practical implementation of the recognition framework. Specifically, the mechanism outlined in the demonstrator integrates and leverages the functionalities of existing researcher profiles and contribution-tracking systems, i.e. APICURON and BIP! Scholar, and their integration with ORCID, enabling the automated and verifiable inclusion of recognition within researchers’ CVs. By building upon the aforementioned infrastructures, the mechanism provides a sustainable approach for embedding recognition into academic and professional narratives.

1 Objectives

The main objective of this milestone is to deliver a working prototype that showcases how third-party recognition of research software-related activities can be seamlessly integrated into researchers' CVs. This includes recognition of a diverse range of contributions including, among others, i) software development and engineering, ii) code maintenance and curation, iii) data stewardship, and iv) delivery of training and capacity-building activities. This mechanism is conceived as a foundational component of the broader recognition framework being developed under Task 5.2 (outlined in deliverable [D5.1 Landscape analysis of existing rewards and mechanisms for research software and training activities](#)). In this context, the milestone also contributes to defining the key stakeholders, relevant components as well as their interactions.

By enabling and leveraging platform-supported recognition of scientific contributions beyond traditional publications, this milestone advances the goal of more inclusive and transparent research assessment practices in line with Open Science principles.

2 Components & Stakeholders

A broader recognition framework was presented at [D5.1](#) report (under Work Package 5 and Task 5.2), acknowledging various platforms supporting recognition, credit and reward of research effort. For the purpose and objectives of the current milestone, the activity recognition mechanism - conceived as a foundational component of this recognition framework - leverages two of these existing platforms (described under Section 4.10 of D5.1), i) **APICURON** (<https://apicuron.org/>), which aggregates activity data from third-party resources to credit and acknowledge scientific contributions through statistics, achievements, and leaderboards and ii) **BIP! Scholar** (<https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/scholar>), an ORCID-linked profiling tool that enriches academic profiles with roles, metrics, and narratives to showcase the breadth and impact of a researcher's work. Together, these platforms complement each other in recognising, crediting, and contextualising research outputs beyond traditional publications. The following components and stakeholders within the broader recognition framework are crucial to the mechanism demonstrated in this specific milestone:

- **Research Publishing Platforms:** these platforms collect, maintain, and publish research assets submitted by researchers. They also gather basic metadata related to the assets. Indicative examples of such platforms include:
 - Research Asset Repositories (e.g., source code repositories, preprint repositories)
 - Research Journals & Publishers
 - Research Activity Registries
- **Researcher PID Providers:** The demonstrated mechanism integrates directly with Researcher Persistent Identifier (PID) providers, e.g. ORCID, to ensure that recognized activities (e.g. those from APICURON and BIP! Scholar) are linked to stable, unique researcher identifiers. This linkage is fundamental for enhancing discoverability and attribution of contributions on a researcher's CV and across the wider ecosystem.
- **Research Metadata Enrichment Services:** While the core of this milestone focuses on the direct integration of existing recognition systems, future iterations of the framework - and by extension, this mechanism - will benefit from services that enrich baseline research asset metadata. These enrichments, whether automatically generated (AI/ML) or human-curated, may include research performance indicators (e.g. citation counts), contribution roles (e.g., [CRedit](#)), and summaries of research topics, which will further enhance the quality of recognition pulled into CVs.
- **Research Metadata Aggregators:** These services collect, merge, clean, and standardize research-related metadata from different sources, providing end users with easy access to the aggregated information. Indicative examples of such services include:
 - Contribution Trackers: collecting asset tracks for researchers, and
 - Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs): universal large-scale aggregators that collect research metadata in a standardized format for analysis, reporting and discovery purposes (e.g. [OpenAlex](#), [OpenAIRE Graph](#))
- **Researcher Contribution Platforms:** This milestone builds on established Researcher Contribution Platforms, which gather detailed research-related information and provide

features (such as analytics, visualizations, gamification features like badges/leaderboards, and profiles) that help recognize and credit researchers' work. The demonstration highlights how recognition from these specific platforms can be extracted and presented for CV inclusion. Indicative examples of such platforms include:

- Reward and Gamification Platforms: services designed to incentivize and acknowledge research efforts, which APICURON and BIP! Scholar exemplify in the context of this milestone's demonstration.
- Academic Profile Platforms: focused on fully recognizing and sharing researchers' contributions. It should be mentioned that BIP! Scholar aims to eventually provide such functionality for Trainers and RSEs through tailored academic profile templates (however the current demonstrator does not cover this aspect at all).

3 Mechanism For Activity Recognition

The proposed mechanism for activity recognition and CV inclusion is built on seamless interactions between the core components and stakeholders described above.

Core platforms involvement

The mechanism primarily integrates APICURON, for tracking research contributions, and BIP! Scholar, for enriching these recognition profiles. These act respectively as “Researcher Contribution Platform” and “Research Metadata Enrichment Service”. In parallel, ORCID serves as “Researcher PID Provider”, ensuring each recognized activity is linked to a unique and stable researcher identity.

Integration and Profile Enhancement

By enabling APICURON and BIP! Scholar to interoperate and share data in compliance with GDPR regulations, the mechanism demonstrates the significant potential of collaboration between both platform contributions. Through existing integrations with PID providers like ORCID, research activities - recognized by the aforementioned platforms - can be directly and automatically incorporated into a researcher’s CV. This showcases a powerful way to enhance a researcher’s professional profile through third-party recognition.

Role of Researcher PID Providers

The mechanism is built on robust integration with Researcher Persistent Identifier (PID) providers, such as ORCID, ensuring that all recognized activities are consistently linked to stable and unique researcher identifiers. This approach strengthens discoverability, supports attribution and promotes interoperability across the system.

Key Implementation Aspects

- **Recognized Activities in APICURON:**

APICURON is specifically designed to track and recognize diverse research activities. Within its structure, “creditors” (e.g. research publishing platforms) define the activities that qualify for recognition. This set of recognized activities is dynamic and meant to evolve in response to new practices in the research software landscape.

- **BIP! Scholar's Role in Recognition Indicators:**

BIP! Scholar plays a crucial role in enriching recognition records by creating an ecosystem of services that provide advanced, transparently calculated, explainable, and well-documented indicators of scientific impact and merit. These indicators are built upon data from popular scientific knowledge bases, such as the OpenAIRE Graph. Within the context of this milestone, BIP! Scholar's contribution ensures that the recognition integrated into CVs is not merely a list of activities but is enriched with quantifiable and understandable measures of impact, supporting scientific discovery and research assessment. This emphasis on explainable

indicators also helps users avoid common pitfalls and misuses in interpreting recognition data.

- **Optimizing the User Journey for CV Inclusion:**

Integrating the CV of a researcher in the user journey is designed to minimize user effort. The only significant point of friction lies in GDPR-compliant consent requirements. Due to the fact that each platform in the framework, such as APICURON and BIP! Scholar, must individually acquire explicit consent from the user. This granular consent is required to process and share personal data tied to a researcher's activities. The multi-platform consent acquisition introduces a notable point of friction for the user throughout their journey, as they must navigate and approve consent requests across different services, which can potentially impede the seamless flow of data and affect the framework's ability to effectively propagate information. Once the necessary consent is granted, the system is designed to enable automatic, privacy-respecting inclusion of recognized contributions into CVs.

4 Demonstration

The demonstration showcases the integration of APICURON with BIP! Scholar statistics to enrich researcher recognition profiles and enable their seamless inclusion in CVs.

The screenshot (Figure 1) presents the publicly accessible APICURON profile of a registered contributor (<https://apicuron.org/curators/0000-0002-0341-4888>), enriched with BIP! Scholar indicators. The upper section of the profile - including the biography, institutional affiliation, research keywords, and social media links - is directly retrieved from the researcher's ORCID record, ensuring persistent and automatically updated personal and professional details. Below this, the profile is complemented by statistics integrated from BIP! Scholar.

The screenshot displays the APICURON profile for Federica Quaglia. The profile includes a biography, place of work (Institute of Biomembranes, Bioenergetics and Molecular Biotechnologies), keywords (biocuration, intrinsically disordered proteins, IDP, DisProt), and social links (ORCID, LinkedIn). Below the biography is the BIP! Scholar Statistics section, which is divided into four categories: Impact Indicators (1318 Citations, 13 Hindex, 7 Influential Works, 18 Popular Works), Productivity Indicators (0 Datasets, 0 Other Works, 24 Papers, 0 Software), Open Science Indicators (7 Open Influential Works, 23 Open Access Works, 96 Open Access Share, 17 Open Popular Works), and Career Stage Indicators (10 Academic Age, 10 Fair Academic Age). The profile also shows earned medals from PED (The Protein Ensemble Database) and DisProt (The database of intrinsically disordered proteins). The PED section includes medals for 'All time best biocurator', 'All time top 10 biocurator', 'All time top 25 biocurator', and 'Best biocurator 2020'. The DisProt section includes medals for 'Top 10 biocurator 2024', 'Top 25 biocurator 2024', 'All time top 10 biocurator', and 'All time top 25 biocurator'. The profile also lists various earned badges and latest contributions for both PED and DisProt.

Figure 1: Overview of a contributor profile in APICURON.

Specifically, the indicators provided by BIP! Scholar include (Figure 2):

- **Impact Indicators:** total Citations, H-index, counts of Influential Works, and Popular Works.
- **Productivity Indicators:** Quantities of Datasets, Papers, Software, and Other Works outputs.
- **Open Science Indicators:** Measures of openly accessible and openly shared works (Open Influential Works, Open Access Works, Open Access Share, Open Popular Works).
- **Career Stage Indicators:** Academic Age and Fair Academic Age metrics.

Figure 2: Overview of a contributor profile in APICURON with focus on the statistics integrated from BIP! Scholar.

Through this integration, APICURON not only records contributions but also contextualises them with transparent, explainable metrics from BIP! Scholar. This enriched, persistently linked profile can be directly exported or referenced in a CV via APICURON's link (e.g. <https://apicuron.org/curators/0000-0002-0341-4888>), enabling automated, verifiable recognition of diverse research activities beyond traditional publications.

5 Summary

This milestone delivers a proof-of-concept mechanism for integrating third-party recognition of research software-related activities into researcher CVs. By combining APICURON's contribution-tracking and gamification features with BIP! Scholar's transparent metrics and indicators, the demonstrator shows how diverse contributions can be both acknowledged and contextualized, providing a comprehensive overview of the researchers' effort and impact.

The approach leverages persistent identifiers (ORCID) to ensure stable attribution, promotes interoperability across recognition platforms, and adheres to GDPR requirements for user consent. Once consent is granted, recognized activities and their associated impact metrics can flow seamlessly into professional profiles and CVs that are maintained by researcher PID Providers that offer academic profiles.

The demonstrated integration not only rewards contributions such as software development, training contributions, data stewardship and biocuration but also aligns with Open Science principles by valuing non-traditional research outputs, far from beyond traditional publications. This work represents a foundational step toward the broader recognition framework under EVERSE WP5, setting the stage for more inclusive and transparent research assessment practices.

6 References

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